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ЭКОЛОГИК ИНҚИРОЗ: КЕЧА ВА БУГУН

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада глобаллашув жараёнлари ҳамда унинг ўзига хос муаммо ва таҳдидлари ҳақида сўз боради. Айнан ана шу таҳдид ва муаммолар доирасидаги экологик инқироз атроф-муҳитга инсон таъсирининг меъёридан ортиши натижасида муносабатларнинг кескинлашуви ҳолатининг кечаги ва бугунги ҳолати ҳамда экомуҳитни келажак авлодлар учун сақлаб қолиш каби долзарб муаммолари хусусида сўз юритилган.

Калит сўзлар: табиат, жамият, экомуҳит, экологик инқироз, экологик таҳдид, экологик муаммо, атроф-муҳит, глобаллашув, келажак авлод, ўтмиш

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ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ КРИЗИС: ВЧЕРА И СЕГОДНЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются процесс глобализации, а также его проблемы и угрозы. Рассматриваются взаимоотношение человека и окружающей среды в условиях уселения антропогенной нагрузки и как следствие обострение данных взаимоотношений в прошлом и сейчас, а также рассматривается проблема сохранения экосреды будущим поколениям.

Ключевые слова: природа, общество, экосфера, экологический кризис, экологическая угроза, экологическая проблема, окружающая среда, глобализация, будущее поколение, прошлое.

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ECOLOGICAL CRISIS: YESTERDAY AND TODAY

ABSTRACT

This article devoted to process of globalization and its problems and threats. Consider mutual relations between human and environment in terms of strengthening anthropogenic loading and as consequence exasperation these relations. Yesterday and now. As is also examines the problem of reservation ecological surroundings for generation which is to come.

Index Terms: nature, society, ecosphere, environmental crisis, environmental threats, environmental problem, globalization, future generation, yesterday, today

While considering current problems, it is clear that globalization process has increased the speed of political activities all around the world. Globalization requires to live in a world of swift, operational activities and make people to live up to date with anthropogenic progress. These conditions lead to the development of consciousness and thinking of human and to the perfection of their lifestyle. Nevertheless, this positive process creates specific problems and threats. It became not only problem of region, nation or country, but also rised to the global level.

Global problems are common phenomenon in all countries and it endangers the entire nations of the world, their life and progress.

Prevention of global warming, fighting against international terrorism, starvation, poverty and illiteracy, protecting the environment from catastrophic pollution, food, industrial raw materials, and shortage of energy resources are the forms of global problems. In other words, it is world scientific-technological, economic, social-political, military processes and their changes.

The term "threat" refers to the fact that it has a certain negative influence in the space and time of "introducing" local, territorial, and regional negative factors that weaken the vital activity, the way of life, the concrete targeted social structure for a specific historical period, or social, historical situation. Let's consider the "human - nature - society" system within these threats and challenges. As a result of technical revolution and inventions in human life, the balance of "human - nature - society" system has disrupted. The XXI century became crucial in the history of human development. The living conditions in the biosphere, which is the habitat of humanity is affected as a result of anthropogenic development. At present, the disruption of natural balance is intensified. These complicated processes requires a deep consideration from humanity.

We need to preserve the environment for future generations. This requires a lot of effort. In particular, it includes protecting the environment from pollution, providing people with drinking water and eco-friendly food products, conservation of biodiversity, climate change prevention, rational use of natural resources and others. The rapid growth of population on the Earth and random use of natural resources caused ecological tension. An ecological threat is a human impact on nature and the reflection of natural impact on human. Human factor plays a main role in influencing the nature. Actually, it is a disruption of balance between man and Earth, and as its scope increases, living conditions and opportunities will decrease as well.

The ecological crisis refers to aggravation of relations as a result of excessive human impact on the environment. This is a tragedy of humanity as well.

It is possible to gain a knowledge from history on solving this problem. In ancient times, humanity aspired to study the natural environment through adaptation, consciousness and thinking. In the process of human society development, the goal of people was to discover new lands, to find and master natural resources. At this stage of development, population growth has affected food insecurity and climatic conditions. Human was powerless against natural forces. For example, abundance of monsoon rains in Ethiopia led to the swamping of the Nile River, and the population had to move to the south. Lower part of Egypt became poor and its political and regional authority were eroded. When the climate was dry, the people returned to their home country and the power of the ancient Egypt began to grow. In the lower stream of the Tigris and Euphrates rivers, as a result of the numerous irrigated land of the ancient Sumerians, salts had grown and the Sumerian culture has failed. Ancient Sumerian died of ecological crisis. Ancient China, while dealing with ecological crisis, has discovered new forms of irrigated agriculture (rice cultivation in the watered areas, fish

breeding) and became increasingly rich. After rebuilding its civilization, China, called its neighbours barbarians, as they could not escape the decline. [3, –Б.121-122.]

In the history of human society, it is clear from these events that disruption of human-nature relations has led to a number of problems. At present, ecological threats are becoming more dangerous in the course of man-made development.

Looking at the evolution of the "nature-human-society" system, five socio-ecological stages can be distinguished.

1. For a long time, people have lived by hunting and depended on food and natural conditions. A thousand years ago, the population of the planet was over 10 million. Over the next three thousand years, food supply has been resolved through the improvement of hunting and hunting tools, animal breeding, and cultivation of some crops. In the primitive farming, with the development of farming and livestock, people began to stay in the same places, and the community began to form.

2. 10,000 years ago, the role of food shortages and restricting natural conditions diminished. The world population had increased over 50 million people. Early ancient cities had appeared and the culture was developed. During this period, an increase of human influence on nature, deforestation, salinization of the land, and initial desertification were observed. As a result of anthropogenic impact, some species of animals became extinct, and some unique plant and animal species had been preserved. This period is called an agrarian stage.

In the Middle Ages, the population exceeded 500 million. In Central Asia, the first ecological knowledge has appeared. Ecological knowledge developed in Europe during the renaissance period. The invention of the steam engine car in 1784 led to the beginning of industrial stage in human history.

4. In the XIX century the population exceeded 1 billion people, the volume of mining and exploitation of natural resources has increased, some species of plants and animals disappeared. The environmental pollution has risen. In the second half of the XIX century, the technogenic stage of society was observed. At that time, ecological threats to humanity appeared.

5. In the second half of the XX century, the improvement in living standards, scientific and technological revolution, and a sharp population growth has led to a "demographic explosion." [4, –Б.14] Growth in the number of population, and increased environmental impact has resulted in global, regional, and global environmental problems. Nuclear energy has been widely used, the planet's life-sustaining environment has seriously damaged the biosphere's stability, forest land has reduced, desertification, decline in the number of animal species, and environmental pollution soared. Now, ecological security is not only national problem, but it has become a global problem for humanity. Nature and man should have relations based on specific rules. Violation of existing laws can lead to irreparable environmental disasters. As the Chinese thinker Lao Tzi states in the doctrine of "daosizm", both nature and society must act according to their own laws, and human should not affect these laws on his own. Otherwise, nature will eventually revenge on humanity.

In the XXI century, it can be seen that the population of our country is facing great ecological risks, as an evidence of above mentioned points. If we will ignore and will not try to do anything about it, then it would be self-destruction.

At present, we divide global problems into three groups:

The first one is contradictory relationship between social forces (socio-economic systems, regional conflicts, national and religious conflicts, etc.) or "intersocial" problems today. War and peace and the use of labor resources are among them.

The second one is the problems connected with the "human - society" system. They include scientific and technological development (STD); education and culture; the rapid growth of population ("demographic explosion"), and the health of people.

The third one is the problems connected with "human - nature" relations. It includes raw material resources, the provision of food, drinking water for people and conservation of nature [4, –Б -14-15].

The above mentioned problems are influenced by human factors and it can be solved by understanding the role and importance of social factors. In the XXI century, a new stage of "human-

nature-society” system development has been established. For this purpose, it is necessary to combine interests of society layers in order to develop ecological consciousness, to provide young generations with comfortable environment and natural resources. It should be noted that the basic anthropogenic and social phenomena goes on in relation with environmental and natural disasters. In order to overcome the ecological crisis, and eliminate the causes preventing from improving the relations, it is necessary to identify and solve them in time. It's time to develop a comprehensive environmental program, according to the recommendations of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). In particular, at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, these global issues were also emphasized. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev in his speech at the UN General Assembly session, stated: "We fully support UN Secretary-General in his position about “the problems of water, peace and security are closely interconnected”. I am convinced that there is no other way to solve the water problem without considering the interests of countries and people of the region. Uzbekistan supports convention projects developed by the UN Regional Center for Preventive Diplomacy on the use of water resources of the Amu Darya and Syrdarya basin. Once again I want to draw your attention to one of the most important environmental problems today - to Aral sea disaster. Here, in my hands, there is a map showing the Aral Sea disaster. I think there is no need to comment on that. Elimination of the sea-related consequences requires an active international engagement”. It is clear from the words of the head of our country that the water-related issue plays an important role in the system of environmental problems in maintaining international peace. Particularly in the territory of Uzbekistan, the rational use of water resources of Amudarya and Syrdarya basins and to eliminate the consequences of the Aral Sea disaster requires international engagement. Because, at present, it is among the most significant environmental problems that affect not only Uzbekistan or Central Asia, but also the whole world.

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ЎТМИШГА НАЗАР

6 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ

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